

AN EDUCATIONAL MOBILE BASED APPLICATION FOR THE VISUALLY IMPAIRED

By

KINOBE JORDAN ATHANASIOS S19B23/160

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTING AND TECHNOLOGY
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING, DESIGN, AND TECHNOLOGY

A Research Project Report Submitted to the Faculty of Engineering, Design, And Technology for the Study Leading to a Project in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Award of the Degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science of Uganda Christian University.

SUPERVISOR

Mr. Joseph Brian Kasozi

MAY 2022.

DECLARATION

I, Kinobe Jordan Athanasius, declare that the content of this research Report was compiled by me and I confirm that this Report is original and has never been presented anywhere for academic purposes or any other purpose.

Signed..........

Date..... 27th May 2022.....

Kinobe Jordan Athanasius

APPROVAL

This is to certify that this Report submitted by Kinobe Jordan Athanasius to the Faculty of Engineering, Design and Technology, Uganda Christian University was carried under my supervision and guidance.

Signed.....

Date... 27th May 2022.....

Mr. Joseph Brian Kasozi

Department of Computing and Technology,

Uganda Christian University.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.

I am most grateful to God Almighty, the sole provider of the knowledge, wisdom, love, mercy and grace for his protection throughout the period of the programme.

I sincerely appreciate my supervisor, Mr. Joseph Brian Kasozi who offered timely criticism and corrections that led me through the various stages of this project.

I appreciate my parents, Mr. John Leonard Kiuwua and Mrs. Grace Asimwe, my siblings and friends for their unquantifiable love and financial assistance during this period. May God bless you in Jesus' name, Amen.

ABSTRACT

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that globally, approximately 1.3 billion people live with some form of visual impairment. The need for developing a low-cost assistive system for the visually impaired and blind people has increased with steady increase in their population worldwide.

The study was guided by the following objectives; To analyze the current system, literature and algorithms used in voice recognition in order to get a profound insight into how they work as well as their weaknesses, to develop the actual system using current technologies such as Google Computer Vision API, to validate the system using data inform of text and speech output from both the visually impaired and normal sighted people so as to check the usefulness of the application.

The study findings revealed that reading for persons who are blind is confined to material such as books, journals etc., that are available in Braille, or to information in audiocassette or electronic formats which gives them limited options and a much slower learning curve as compared to their normal sighted counterparts.

This research may well be a survey on a solution to help the visually impaired using computer science, Voice Recognition and Image Recognition. The solution is implemented by developing an Android Application which could assist the user using voice command, recognizing and analyzing the text from documents and providing suitable response in speech format. It provides an efficient way by which visually impaired people are able to read and consume information from digitally printed documents not limited to braille throughout their educational journey using their smartphone.

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT.....	5
Chapter One.....	8
1.1 Introduction	8
1.2 Background	8
1.3 Problem statement	12
1.4 General Objective	13
1.5 Specific objectives	14
1.6 Scope of the Study	14
1.7 Significance of the study	15
CHAPTER 2: Literature Review	16
2.1 Introduction	16
2.2 What is visual impairment and what is the role of mobile devices in solving such issues?	16
2.3 Audio Books.....	17
An Interactive Mobile Application for the Visually Impaired to Have Access to Listening Audio Books with Handy Books Portal.....	17
2.4 Paper 2: A Smart Personal AI Assistant for Visually Impaired People	19
2.5 How does the application work?.....	19
2.6 Conclusion	21
CHAPTER 3: Methodology	22
3.1 Introduction	22
3.2 Area of study	22
3.3 Study population.....	22
3.4 Research design and development method.....	22
3.5 Sampling Procedures	25
3.6 Sample size	25

3.7	Sampling technique	26
3.8	Data collection techniques.....	26
3.9	Proposed Technologies.....	26
CHAPTER FOUR: System Analysis and Design		28
4.1	Study of Current System.....	28
4.2	Proposed System	30
4.3	System Design	32
Chapter Five: Evaluation		36
5.1	Digital Document in English	36
5.2	Experiment Setup.....	37
5.3	Experiment Platform	37
5.3.1	Software specification	37
5.4	Experiment Results	38
5.4.1	Validation Results	39
5.5	Conclusion	43
Chapter Six: Limitation, Conclusion, and Future Work		44
6.1	Limitation.....	44
6.2	Conclusion	44
6.3	Future Work	44
References		45
Appendix		49

Chapter One

1.1 Introduction

According to the World Health Organization estimation, globally the number of people with some visual impairment is estimated to be 285 million, of whom 39 million are blind (M, et al., 2019). The inability to use features such as reading of newspapers, journals, textbooks, path finding or outdoor navigation and reading SMS is a disadvantage for blind people in many professional and educational situation.

They suffer in strange surroundings without any manual aid. Visual information is the basis for most tasks, so visually impaired people are at disadvantage because necessary information about the surrounding environment is not available. With the recent advances in inclusive technology, it is possible to extend the support given to people with visual impairment.

1.2 Background

The estimation of 285 million people suffering from visually impairment worldwide are divided into two groups of 39 million blind and 246 million with low vision. That means that someone in our world goes blind in every five seconds. Demographics of the blindness vary significantly in different parts of the world. In developing countries, about 0.4 % of the population is blind while in the rest part of the world this rate rises up to 1 %. Consequently, 90 % of the visually impaired population are living in developing countries. About 82 % of the blind are over the age of 50. (Anon., 2017)

(a) Normal vision

(b) Central cataract

(c) Half vision

(d) Central loss of vision

Four examples of different kind of vision and visual impairment

It is important to distinguish between different kind of visually impairment, as each type are causing different problems which requires different kind of solutions and contextual information necessary.

The figure above shows some different kind of visual impairment and how it can affect the visual information available compared to normal vision.

There are also several different degrees of visual impairment and according to WHO, vision function is classified in four levels as follows:

- Normal (full) vision - no visual impairment
- Moderate vision impairment
- Severe vision impairment
- Blindness

Moderate vision impairment combined with severe vision impairment are grouped under the term “low vision”: low vision taken together with blindness represents all vision impairment. About 15 % of people who are having vision loss cannot see anything at all. The remaining 85-90 % may have residual vision or other types of low vision and may have difficulties with color, light, form or movement perception.

Visual acuity is a number used by eye care professionals that indicates the sharpness or clarity of vision. A visual acuity measurement of 20/70 means that a person with 20/70 vision who is standing 20 feet (approximately 6,1 meter) from an eye chart sees what a person with unimpaired (or 20/20) vision can see from 70 feet (approximately 21.3 meter) away.

Approximately 12 million people 40 years and over in the United States have vision impairment, including 1 million who are blind, 3 million who have vision impairment after correction, and 8 million who have vision impairment due to uncorrected refractive error.

As of 2012, 4.2 million Americans aged 40 years and older suffer from uncorrectable vision impairment, out of which 1.02 million who are blind; this number is predicted to more than

double by 2050 to 8.96 million due to the increasing epidemics of diabetes and other chronic diseases and our rapidly aging U.S. population.

Approximately 6.8% of children younger than 18 years in the United States have a diagnosed eye and vision condition. Nearly 3 percent of children younger than 18 years are blind or visually impaired, defined as having trouble seeing even when wearing glasses or contact lenses.

The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) reports that every day about 2,000 U.S. workers sustain job-related eye injuries that require medical treatment. However, safety experts and eye doctors believe the right eye protection can lessen the severity or even prevent 90 percent of these eye (Anon., 2020)

In Uganda, a survey was carried out on childhood blindness and low vision and a category of 14.8% had visual impairment, 6.5% severe visual impairment, 63.2% were blind and 15.2% were too young to test. The acuities and causes were similar in school and community groups, excepting cortical visual impairment and multiple impairment, which are much commoner in the community. Cataract was the largest cause of visual impairment(30.7%) and surgical outcome was unsatisfactory. Visual loss following corneal ulceration was the second commonest cause of subnormal vision (22.0%) (KM, 2010)

Cataract and corneal damage cause half of all subnormal vision, which is avoidable for both. Cataract surgery needs to be upgraded. To prevent corneal visual loss, primary health care should continue to be expanded, especially measles immunization and nutrition care; rubella immunization is being added too. Public perceptions need changing for results to be improved and help offered to more than the present minority.

Unlike their sighted counterparts, reading for persons who are blind is confined to material such as books, journals, magazines and newsletters that are available in Braille, or to information in audiocassette or electronic formats. They do not have the benefit of incidental reading material such as street signs, advertisements on billboards, package labels, or the wording in television commercials.

An important observation is that young children who are blind often miss out on the purposes of reading and writing because, unlike their sighted peers, they do not observe their family members engaging in writing or reading activities, such as reading the

newspaper, drawing up shopping lists, jotting down telephone numbers, or consulting a recipe card (Swenson 1988:337).

The role of parents in minimizing this drawback is often emphasized, as children need to be made aware at an early age of the value of a reading and writing medium if they are to meet the diverse challenges of education. This issue is underscored by Swenson (1988:337) who maintains that parents need to realize that, even though print is an abstract concept for most children who are blind, they can and should be made aware of its many uses. Parents should describe in simple terms what they are reading or writing. Later, when children who are blind begin reading Braille and writing with the Braillewriter, their basic understanding of why people read and write would give them many reasons to practice and enjoy their new skills.

Unquestionably, although Swenson (1988:337) emphasizes the importance of building a solid foundation for reading and writing in Braille, the argument would apply equally to reading and writing/recording through other media, such as audiotapes, computers with speech output, and optical character recognition document readers (OCR scanners). Essentially, if children who are blind are not aware of the value of reading and writing, and if they do not enjoy reading and writing, they would be reluctant to use the various reading and writing media available to them.

This idea is also explored by Bettelheim and Zelan (1982:48) who observe that well-meaning educators frequently implore learners to apply themselves more assiduously to learn reading skills, so that they would be able to "get ahead in the world." They (Bettelheim & Zelan 1982:48) argue that children are not strongly motivated by distant rewards. They need to believe that reading is a pleasurable activity, which educators, their parents and other adults engage in as well.

In underscoring the importance of activities to promote reading as a pleasurable activity, Southgate (1984:9) maintains that teachers of reading should draw from a wide repertoire of activities to promote reading skills. This idea is reinforced by Phillips 6 (1984:14) who asserts that teachers should not only understand the objectives of teaching reading, they should be flexible in applying a programme that responds to the needs, interests and abilities of learners.

An important consideration is that children who are blind should be given the reassurance that the reading and writing media used by persons who are blind are really alternate ways

to reading and writing. This would result in a positive attitude to these media, particularly when they realize that these media are just as valuable as the print medium. Moreover, the provision of first-hand experiences in the use of the various reading and writing media would overcome any resistance to these media, as it could potentially be the media they would use for their reading and writing tasks.

Admittedly, as with the print medium, a positive attitude to and respect for the various reading and writing media used by persons who are blind would be inculcated only if these qualities are displayed by parents and educators. Equally important, educators must have the necessary training in the various reading and writing media if they are to impart any meaningful skills to their learners.

The currently existing system uses speech synthesis to read e-books for the visually impaired using mobile application and converts the document/soft copy of the books to the speech using natural language and Text-to-Speech.

Major problem with the existing system is that it works only for single language (English), and not compatible with other languages. It does not work offline and always requires internet connection for the feedback/response.

It is therefore in this regard that the study seeks to develop a mobile phone based educational application that will aid the visually impaired people throughout their educational journey where the application will provide an answer to an educational query where the user will take pictures of text they want to hear from content shared to them by their tutors or even help them read other material such as novels by extracting the text from images and reading them out for them in voice format hence it will support speech recognition for the user input.

1.3 Problem statement

The visually impaired are faced with challenges such as being unable to read educational materials for example books, magazines, journals, novels, newspapers, digital official documents such as certificates and any other digitally printed documents such as pdfs with study material that they are required to consume by their teachers but without the aid of an external tutor, they are unable to make use of such important documents like being able to read newspapers to find out the current affairs, reading novels during their leisure time. This can be supported by the statistics that indicate that people around the world

have visual impairment and that Uganda is among the most affected “Over 1.2 million people are visually impaired through shortsightedness whereas 250,000 (0.4% of the population) are totally blind in Uganda. (Kazibwe, 2016)

Unlike their sighted counterparts, reading for persons who are blind is confined to material such as books, journals, magazines and newsletters that are available in Braille, or to information in audiocassette or electronic formats. They do not have the benefit of incidental reading material such as street signs, advertisements on billboards, package labels, or the wording in television commercials.

An important observation is that young children who are blind often miss out on the purposes of reading and writing because, unlike their sighted peers, they do not observe their family members engaging in writing or reading activities, such as reading the newspaper, drawing up shopping lists, jotting down telephone numbers, or consulting a recipe card (Swenson 1988:337).

The above-mentioned problems have motivated this research to come up with a localized automated solution to aid the visually impaired people through their education by use of a mobile application that makes use of some of the existing architecture such as the Microsoft Cognitive computer vision API as well as the tesseract Open-Source OCR Engine for Optical Character Recognition which will aid in extraction of digital and hand written text from images and be able to read them out in speech format that they can easily understand.

1.4 General Objective

The general objective of this project is to develop an education mobile phone-based application which will give the visually impaired people the ability to listen to text read to them from the application, define their own educational questions and answers as it will have the capability to get the input as speech format from the visually impaired person. Basing on this, they will therefore not need to type on the keyboard to provide input. They will just be required to touch their phone screen which loads up the camera and be able to take pictures or images of the text in front of them. Output of the application will be given as both text and speech format so that the user can be able to hear their output. Therefore, this application will serve as new platform for a visually impaired people in their education.

1.5 Specific objectives

- To analyze the current system, tools, literature and algorithms used in voice recognition in order to get a profound insight into how they work as well as their weaknesses to aid the visually impaired people.
- To develop the actual system using current technologies such as Azure Cognitive services Computer Vision API, the Optical character recognition client library and REST API and Java for the mobile application. The system will preferably be built on the cloud for scalability and efficiency purposes.
- To validate the system using data inform of text and speech input from both the visually impaired and normal sighted people so as to check the usefulness of the application and increase the accuracy of the system.

1.6 Scope of the Study

Geographical Scope

The aim of the proposal is to undertake the research with a view to shedding light on the impact that the different reading and writing media have on the education of blind persons with in central Uganda and to develop a mobile phone-based application to aid the visually impaired people through their educational journey so that they are able to listen to both digital and hand written text being read to them from the application by use of mobile phone camera. The following goals will assist in highlighting the salient issues in this study:

- To trace the development of tactual reading media as part of an historical background to blindness.
- To discuss the major challenges faced by blind persons in education in central Uganda.
- To evaluate the reading media used by persons who are blind.
- To research the impact of the different reading media on the education of persons who are blind.

Time Scope

The project shall run through and be completed within the year 2022.

1.7 Significance of the study

This study is aimed at drawing attention towards the educational journey of the visually impaired people as it will aid them in seeking answers to questions so that they are able to access the same resources as everyone else that were previously not available to them since they are not able to see and without necessarily being assisted by a physical person. This study is also aimed at laying a foundation on which other innovative educational speech synthesis systems and systems for extraction of digital and hand written text from images for the visually impaired can be built.

CHAPTER 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Numerous studies have been conducted focusing on people with disabilities from a sociological point of view. People with disabilities face significant inequity of remuneration, globally, due to the perception of a lack of skills, proper education and employment accommodation for particular roles.

This section of the paper looks at a review of papers that have been written about existing applications for visually impaired people. In this section, two papers were looked at.

2.2 What is visual impairment and what is the role of mobile devices in solving such issues?

Many people have some type of visual problem at some point in their lives. Some can no longer see objects far away. Others have problems reading small print. These types of conditions are often easily treated with eyeglasses or contact lenses.

But when one or more parts of the eye or brain that are needed to process images become diseased or damaged, severe or total loss of vision can occur. In these cases, vision can't be fully restored with medical treatment, surgery, or corrective lenses like glasses or contacts.

The American Foundation for the Blind estimates that 10 million people in the United States are visually impaired. Visual impairment is a term experts use to describe any kind of vision loss, whether it's someone who cannot see at all or someone who has partial vision loss. (Jonathan, 2016)

Some people are completely blind, but many others have what's called legal blindness. They haven't lost their sight completely but have lost enough vision that they'd have to stand 20 feet from an object to see it as well as someone with perfect vision could from 200 feet away.

Mobile phones are widely used in modern society, especially among users with visual impairments; they are considered the most helpful tool for blind users to communicate with people worldwide (Smaradottir & Haland, 2017). In addition, the technology of touch screen assistive technology enables speech interaction between blind people and mobile devices and permits the use of gestures to interact with a touch user interface. Assistive technology is vital in helping people living with disabilities perform actions or interact with systems

2.3 Audio Books

An Interactive Mobile Application for the Visually Impaired to Have Access to Listening Audio Books with Handy Books Portal

U.Avanthika, Shyam Sundar and Silviya Nancy from Saveetha University, Chennai, India wrote this paper with the objective to propose a completely new idea having a portal where visually impaired people can store audio books aided with interactive system so that they can use them whenever they are needed (Avanthika, et al., 2015)

Objectives

To analyze the current system, tools, literature and algorithms used in voice recognition in order to get a profound insight into how they work as well as their weaknesses to aid the visually impaired people.

What is the paper's main objective?

The main objective of this paper was to propose a portal for visually impaired people to store their audio books through an interactive system and be able to access them at any particular time.

What does the paper say about visually impaired people ?

The paper addresses a problem of blind people being a step backward in using mobile application. For them, they are limited to use mobile for communicating to each other in a basic mode. Here with advancements in educational institutions. The blind are usually away from learning portals because of their disabilities.

What models are being used in achieving their objective ?

The paper points out the use of a mobile reader for visually disabled as the voice interface by the proposed model Tyflo recognizes specific command. When user speaks, it maps the word from the command database, works accordingly and brings out the desired output on to the screen.

The paper uses the voice user interface to interact with the blind. With their app installed, the blind can login to the portal; they are availed with books listed available which is read

out by the voice in the app. They can choose which ever book they want and they can listen to it ultimately reducing the waiting time for scribes.

How does their application work?

The paper achieves its main objective as stated through the following processes: This application has a backup database, which runs once the application is turned ON.

The application then automatically generates the audio response to notify that the application is ON. It asks the user to choose between the available domains. Once the user chooses "COURSE MATERIALS", the educational & course related audio book list is read out by the voice user interface (VUI).

If the user chooses the other available category, "Leisure books", all the other books from various domains are read out again to the auditory of the user by the Voice User Interface (VUI) again.

After it reads out, there is a pause for user to give out response. The user should specify the filename or the keyword related to the book; the application will search the database and will call for the next possible command. If the book is not available, it notifies that too.

When the user asks the application to read the book, the response & voice output modules work accordingly to start the playing of the specified audio book.

I therefore look forward to implementing similar functionality in my application for providing fast voice input to output responses to aid the visually impaired in their educational journey.

What are the strengths and weakness?

This paper was able to achieve the objective set forth and enable visually impaired people make use of this application to update themselves in various domains with reading books and not limited to using mobile phones for calling in their case hence with the development of Virtual OS and the Voice User Interface (VUI) they can develop their knowledge with this application.

The application is however limited to providing literature or books related to what the user has typed it but doesn't give account for if the user had a specific query, he or she was looking for over the internet for example an answer to a particular educational question.

It is also limited in that there is need for the user to click somewhere on the screen which limits the visually impaired who cannot see at all and will require an external assistant to aid them in the navigation to get to what they need.

In my work, I shall be able to minimize the number of interactions the user has to do to just launching the application and navigating using both voice commands and button clicks.

2.4 Paper 2: A Smart Personal AI Assistant for Visually Impaired People

A Smart Personal AI Assistant for Visually Impaired People is an application developed for android platform and is the second paper I have reviewed. It uses Google Vision API for Image recognition and also provides functionalities to recognize text from a .pdf file which is then read aloud using text-to-speech engine provided by google. It uses device camera to capture image and requires a network connection for the image to be processed by google vision API. (Felix, et al., 2018)

What modules were used in developing the application?

Image Recognition YOLO (You Only Look Once) real-time object detection algorithm, which is one of the most effective object detection algorithms that consists of many of many ideas coming out of the computer vision research community. Object detection is a critical capability of autonomous vehicle technology.

Speech Recognition is used in the application to understand user's query and respond to it. The user can ask for surrounding information, to which the application will provide information such as objects in the image detected and their distances using Speech synthesis. If the user is walking, then the speech synthesis will be used to inform user that there is an obstacle of the way.

In my application, I am looking at integrating and implementing speech and image recognition for users to be able to take pictures and the application should be able to read text off of the images taken from the mobile device camera.

2.5 How does the application work?

The Application requires a bot to perform interaction with the end-user which is done using Dialog Flow API. DialogFlow is a platform for building natural and rich conversational experiences. Google uses its own implementation of Dialog Flow which can use Cloud Text-

toSpeech powered by DeepMind WaveNet to generate speech responses. This conversion from intent text responses to audio is known as audio output, speech synthesis, text-to-speech or TTS.

What are the strength and weakness of the application?

In this paper, they implemented the technology that attempts to make the lives of Visually Impaired people easier by providing them a visual aid.

A Chatbot application was implemented which enables the visually impaired to feel the surrounding up to certain extent using Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Technology.

The chatbot provided friendly interaction and further made it easy to interact with the application. It also eliminated the need to physically interact with the device. This was because, we are directly interacting with the application using voice command. Therefore, this application enabled visually challenged people to improve their lifestyle.

What are the major drawbacks of their application and how they will this be controlled in my proposed system?

The system is limited in a way that it requires a full-time connection to the internet in order to operate at its best capacity and rather, my solution is to provide an application that can work both online and offline even when one has no connection to the internet, it will be able to give them some kind of feedback during operation.

The other draw back about their application is that it is limited to Hindu, and Indian native language which does not suite the visually impaired population in Uganda. In my application, I shall be able to provide English language which is a universal language for most people located within central Uganda and is within the scope of my research.

2.6 Conclusion

The technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning plays a vital role in the development of the IT sector. Different researchers have made use of these technologies for the visually impaired people so that they too can lead a normal and independent life like other people. Text recognition helps in reading and analyzing text. It is for this reason therefore, that this study will apply machine learning and artificial intelligence as well as text and speech recognition to achieve the purpose of this study.

CHAPTER 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with the steps and procedures that are going to be taken to achieve the main objective of this report which is to develop an educational android-based application that will provide the answer for educational based queries for the visually impaired people in their study purpose. Furthermore, the chapter goes in detail to spell out the procedure that is to be followed in detail, the technologies as well as the work plan and budget.

3.2 Area of study

The chosen area of study will be the visually impaired people who are looking to find answers to their educational queries. They are able to launch the application by passing in voice commands which are captured by Google's voice assistant which then helps to launch the application and then be able to interact with it thereafter.

3.3 Study population

The study population for this paper will comprise of the visually impaired people with in central Uganda who are looking to gain educational resources throughout their day-to-day study activities.

3.4 Research design and development method

The chosen methodology for the proposed system will be extreme programming which is under agile methodology.

Extreme Programming (XP) is a software engineering process, which uses Agile Software Development Methodology and was first introduced by Kent Beck in 1996. With traditional software development methodologies which most of them are linear, one of the problems most software development methodologies had was not being cost-effective for companies because the requirements always were changing and modifying those new requirements could cost a lot and that was the period when Extreme Programming was introduced. Extreme Programming is beneficial when requirements change frequently, which introduces barriers where new requirements can be altered.

Some of the points of using Extreme Programming are as follows and they may be considered an advantage or disadvantage depending on individual software engineers and individual

clients: Organized programming, Fewer mistakes, Programmer and client satisfaction, Customer has control, Test Iterations, Methodology rules, Client initials requirements. (Azimi, 2017)

The main goal of Extreme programming is to develop quality software

Extreme Programming has several life-cycle phases and these include:

Phase 1- Planning

This is the first phase of Extreme programming which involves user stories along with iterations. Planning is further divided into two other phases namely;

Release planning:

Here we discover what needs to be done and identifying the priority tasks as well as focus on what requirements are needed in the near-term releases and when they should be delivered.

Where are we now, where do we need to be and what needs to be done.

Exploration:

Here the customer provides a list of high priority requirements of the system.

Commitment:

Here the business team and Developers commit themselves to the functionality that will be included to the day of the next release and when are the tasks to be performed going to be done.

Steering:

Requirements can be adjusted and new requirements are added. Flexibility in the planning because things change and we have to be flexible with the demands of the user.

Iterative Planning

Exploration phase:

Here we break the user requirements into small tasks and tasks be used to be completed with-in the time limit.

Commitment phase:

Here developers make commitment to achieve the set tasks in the given time.

Steering phase

Here is the flexibility and change of the original user stories.

Under the planning phase, for my case , the customers will be the visually impaired people who I shall interact with and ask about the needs they might require from the application to be able to help them out in their educational journey. These will be the requirements that will be put in form of user stories.

Phase 2 - Designing

After the plan is ready with its iterations, the designing process will come into effect. For the design, I will make use of designing software such as Visual Paradigm or draw.io that shall be used to design the use case diagrams as well as the activity diagrams for the application to be built.

I shall also put flow chart diagrams since they will be able to show the system flow of how the application runs right from the time a user launches it, to when it is closed by the user as well as a logical database design of the system.

Phase 3 - Coding

Coding is the most vital phase of the life cycle stages because with extreme programming, it has priority over all other tasks. The format and style of coding must be unchanged so as to enable compatibility among the team. It results in faster and wider teamwork. This phase includes pair programming, regular integration and firm observances such as 40-hour work weeks with no overtimes, code review, and refactoring.

Under this phase, the technologies to be put to use will include Visual Studio code which is an Integrated Development Environment, Android studio for building native android applications using JAVA programming language, Tensor flow and Keras-OCR for training a machine learning model to be able to extract text from images.

Phase 4 - Testing

In Extreme Programming, testing always comes with coding and development stages rather than after the completion. Occasionally, there are developers that write the tests first and write the code later because that will give them some idea of what their codes need to do.

These are called unit tests and the purpose of doing them is to remove bugs before the delivery.

In the application to be developed for the visually impaired, unit tests will be carried out at every stage along-side the coding in order to minimize errors and improve on the quality of the code. Unit tests ensure that all code meets quality standards before deployment and this ensures a reliable engineering environment where quality is paramount and it also helps developers write better code more efficiently.

Tests and validations will be carried out on the model to check whether it performs as expected.

Phase 5 - Listening

The basis of extreme programming is a continuous mechanism of customer involvement through feedback during the development phase. The basis of feedback is customer acceptance tests and each feedback of the customer that specifies revised requirement becomes the basis of a new design, and the process of design-coding-tests-listening repeats itself. If the customer remains satisfied with the test results the iteration ends there and the design for the new iteration starts which again follows the design-coding-testing-listening cycle. (Anon., 2010)

3.5 Sampling Procedures

This section looks at sampling generally which is a process used in statistical analysis in which a predetermined number of observations are taken from a larger population. The section will include the sample size and the technique to be used in the final project development.

3.6 Sample size

Sample size is a count of individual samples or observations in any statistical setting. For the proposed project, a total of 20 visually impaired people will be used to test the application as well as a number of different questions will be submitted into the application in order to find out the output and determine the accuracy of the output with both text and speech input. The visually impaired people will be sourced from various NGOs that deal with the specific category in Uganda.

3.7 Sampling technique

Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. Using this sampling, the strata are will be formed basing on shared attributes or characteristics such as total blindness, or half blindness. This technique is to be used because it will enable the researcher to obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied and also it divides the population into homogeneous groups which makes each sample equally likely to occur hence increased accuracy of the modal.

3.8 Data collection techniques

This section of the proposal looks at requirements which are key for the development of the tool. A requirement refers to a description of features and functionalities of the target system. Requirements convey the expectations of users. In order to gather the business, functional and non-functional requirements the questionnaires technique is as the primary technique for requirements gathering, which will be designed and distributed in order to obtain the requirements. This is the chosen technique because it addresses the area of scalability where by it can be shared through the internet, it is cost effective, efficient due to the flexibility given to the recipient. Furthermore, the technique will be easy to work with in terms of interpreting and extraction of data.

3.9 Proposed Technologies

The system will be accessed through an internet-based android application that makes use of text and speech synthesis to interact with the user. The technologies that may be used are as follows:

- Java which is a high-level programming language widely used in developing and writing programs for native android mobile based applications.
- Tensor flow which is and end-to-end open-source platform for machine learning. It has a comprehensive, flexible ecosystem of tools, libraries that helps researcher push the state-of-the-art in Machine Learning and developers easily build and deploy Machine Learning powered applications.

- Cloud Vision API which offers powerful pre-trained machine learning models through REST and RPC APIs. Assign labels to images and quickly classify them into millions of predefined categories. Detect printed and handwritten text and build valuable metadata into the image catalog.
- Keras which allows users to productize deep model on smartphones (iOS and Android), on the web, or on the Java Virtual Machine. It allows use of distributed training of deep-learning models on clusters of Graphics processing units (GPU) and tensor processing unit (TPU). Keras-ocr provides out-of-the-box OCR models and an end-to-end training pipeline to build new OCR models (keras_ocr, 2019).
- It also includes AB library which is provided by the ALICE (Artificial Linguistic Internet Computer Entity) (Dhavare & Kulkarni, 2015) which handle the AIML (Artificial Intelligence Markup Language) files.
- The AB library handles the AIML files which has the predefined questions and answers within a proper AIML tags
- After getting the result from the resource, output will be given as speech by the TTS which converts the text to speech. Output will be provided in both text and speech form.
- Further, in AIML information retrieval is based on four pattern matching techniques they are, symbolic reduction, divide and conquer, synonyms resolution, keywords detection. These methods are predefined in AB library.

CHAPTER FOUR: System Analysis and Design

This chapter describes, in detail, the steps, tools and methods used to achieve the purpose of this study which is to develop a mobile based application for visually impaired people that can aid them in reading digitally and hand written information and other study material. In this chapter we look deeper into the different possibilities with voice control and haptic interfaces as well as the concept of multimodal and context-aware interfaces.

4.1 Study of Current System

This section describes the analysis done on an existing system for aiding the visually impaired to read through an application and providing a summary of the pros and cons.

System Overview

Blind Reader: An Intelligent Assistant for Blind is an Android Application (Shahed & Md, 2016). It used Speech Synthesis and Text Recognition to recognize the text from a pdf file and synthesize it to the user. A text document or a .ppt file is converted into a .pdf by recognizing a collection of words. As the application is built on android, it uses pre-defined APIs for text-to-speech conversion which makes the process even more efficient. It uses Google Vision API for Image recognition and also provides functionalities to recognize text from a .pdf file which is then read aloud using text-to-speech engine provided by google. It uses device camera to capture image and requires a network connection for the image to be processed by google vision API.

Speech Recognition is used in the application to understand user's query and respond to it. The user can ask for surrounding information, to which the application will provide information such as objects in the image detected and their distances using Speech synthesis. If the user is walking, then the speech synthesis will be used to inform user that there is an obstacle of the way. The user's speech is given as input which is then converted to binary data and then sent to server for analysis. A suitable response is generated and sent to the application. Application requires a bot to perform interaction with the end-user which is done using Dialog Flow API. DialogFlow is a platform for building natural and rich conversational experiences. Google uses its own implementation of Dialog Flow which can use Cloud Text-toSpeech powered by DeepMind WaveNet to generate speech responses.

This conversion from intent text responses to audio is known as audio output, speech synthesis, text-to-speech or TTS.

Strengths

- It delivers natural and rich conversational experiences using Natural Language Processing and carry forward conversation in a natural way. Machine learning makes Dialogflow intelligent enough to predict the hidden intention expressed in the natural input language.
- A Dialogflow chatbot can map the user's query with the database available with its backend server. The mechanism of mapping is called as Intent.
- It uses a YOLO(You only Look Once) algorithm for real-time object detection which has a very high computation speed of (45 frames per second better than real time). Network understands generalized object representation allowing allowed to train the network on real world images and predictions on artwork are still fairly accurate.
- The network uses features from the entire image to predict each bounding box. It also predicts all bounding boxes across all classes for an image simultaneously.
- The YOLO design enables end-to-end training and real time speeds while maintaining high average precision.
- Being an API, it is independent of the platform it is running on making it a cross-platform able to run on all devices.

Weaknesses

- It requires a stable and working internet connection for it to be able to communicate to the Google Cloud Vision Server through the Application Programming Interfaces and for the images to be processed.
- It requires some level of external assistance from a none visually impaired personnel to help out the visually impaired individual since it involves having to make several clicks on the application to navigate to the desired goal hence it is not fully convenient for the visually impaired since they aren't able to see what they are clicking. For example, being able to locate the microphone button to capture input.
- Another problem with this implementation is that as the complexity increases, the image recognition performance degrades as more processing is required to convert

RGB to HIS since it also uses camera to capture images using the RGB camera which is then converted to Hue Saturation Intensity and then object is detected.

- It is also subject to bias and misreporting.
- Unsuitable for visually impaired individuals that are fully blind with no vision at all.

4.2 Proposed System

In this section, I first give an overview of the proposed educational based mobile application for visually impaired people for scanning and reading text in both digital and hand written format, which is then converted to speech for the blind people to listen to the output. Then I discuss the implementation details of each component of the system.

System Overview

In this project, I propose to implement the proposed system and the features it will contain using text to speech conversion as well as Optical Character Recognition. Hence, a solution to the problem will be provided.

A simple diagram to provide an overview of functionality is given below as well as the main steps involved in the proposed system

1. First, the document, image or written text required to be read out to the visually impaired person is provided to the system.
2. Next, the document or scanned text from the image is then checked if it is in the right language which is by default English and also taken from the right view point i.e., an upright document that is not upside down.
3. The image will then undergo processing i.e., the image is taken and is converted to gray scale image. The gray scale image is then converted to binary image. This process is called Digitization of image or Binarization.
4. Practically any scanner is not perfect; the scanned image may have some noise. This noise may be due to some unnecessary details present in the image. By applying suitable methods, the denoised image is produced. The denoised image thus obtained is saved for further processing.
5. After the recognition stage, if there are some unrecognized characters found, those characters are given their meaning in the post-processing stage. Extra templates can be added to the system for providing a wide range of compatibility checking in the systems database.

6. Then finally, the scanned text image or document is then read out to the visually impaired user in the form of text to speech and they are able to listen to the desired output.

Overview of the Proposed System

Functional Requirements

These are descriptions of the services that the application must offer. The application should perform the following functionalities:

1. The system should be able to scan all types of text documents both digital format and hand written in English language.
2. The system should be able to read out the text to the visually impaired user just by the tap of the screen. Speech should be in English.
3. System should be able to display the scanned text while it is performing the scanning of the text presented to it to confirm that what it has read out is actually what is expected.

Non-Functional requirements

These specify the criteria that can be used to judge the operation of a system, rather than the specific behaviors. The system should perform the following:

1. The system should be accessible from any android device that has a camera for scanning.

2. The system should provide immediate response to the user once it has successfully scanned the text.

4.3 System Design

This section defines the elements of the system such as image recognition module and character extraction.

Design

Use case diagram

Flow Chart Diagram

The workflow of this educational application for the visually impaired is shown above.

Once the application has opened, the user will have to hold the mobile device at a distance above the text to be read. The user will then touch the screen of the mobile device and

the application will be able to read the text presented to it from the camera of the application. The application retrieves the result from the use of the mobile-vision API as well as tensor flow.

The system design phase is one of the most crucial segments of the proposed system because it looks at the process of designing the elements of a system such as the architecture, modules and components, the different interfaces of those components and the data that goes through that system as shown by the flow diagram.

A database is used at the back end for recognition. In proposed system the process consists of following processing steps:

- Scanning of Image
- Pre-processing of Image
- Character Extraction
- Feature Extraction and Recognition
- Post-Processing.

In the document scanning step, a scanner is used to scan the handwritten or printed documents. The quality of the scanned document depends up on the scanner. So, a scanner with high speed and color quality is desirable. The recognizing process includes several complex algorithms and previously loaded templates and dictionary which are crosschecked with the characters in the document and the corresponding machine editable ASCII characters. The verifying is done either randomly or chronologically by human Intervention (Pranob, Harish, & Swathi, 2012).

A. Preprocessing

The image is taken and is converted to gray scale image. The gray scale image is then converted to binary image. This process is called Digitization of image (Binarization). Practically any scanner is not perfect; the scanned image may have some noise. This noise may be due to some unnecessary details present in the image. By applying suitable methods, the denoised image is produced. The denoised image

thus obtained is saved for further processing (Combination of Document Image Binarization Techniques, 2011).

B. Character Extraction

The pre-processed image serves as the input to this and each single character in the image is found out (Tariq & Umar, 2010).

C. Recognition

The image from the extraction stage is correlated with all the templates which are preloaded into the system. Once the correlation is completed, the template with the maximum correlated value is declared as the character present in the image.

D. Post Processing

After the recognition stage, if there are some unrecognized characters found, those characters are given their meaning in the post-processing stage. Extra templates can be added to the system for providing a wide range of compatibility checking in the systems database (Pranob, Harish, & Swathi, 2012).

Chapter Five: Evaluation

This chapter presents the results and findings from building the mobile application, experimental settings and setup as well as the extraction of text from printed documents.

5.1 Digital Document in English

In this project, a document printed in English was used for the scanner to be able to scan the image of the text and extract the text which is to be translated in the text to speech format.

The image was zoomed in, in order to capture the best match of the text presented to the system clearly.

Some example text being scanned by the application.

5.2 Experiment Setup

The system depends on training samples as input data. In this work, database of (91) samples were collected from the data sets shown in Table (1) below for different font types ("Arial", "Calibri", "Courier New", "Lucida Sans" and "Times New Roman") and for different font sizes (8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20) to produce (3185) samples.

Table (1): Data-Set Samples

NO.	Data sets	No. of Samples	Samples
1	Digits	10	0 1 2 ... 9
2	Capital English Letters	26	'A' 'B' 'C' ... 'Z'
3	Small English Letters	26	'a' 'b' 'c' ... 'z'
4	Some common ASCII Symbols	29	. , ; ' " : [] - + * / = () { } < > ! @ # \$ % ^ & ? \ _

5.3 Experiment Platform

I implemented the read-for-me application using the google android gms vision API, which includes different interfaces and classes for identifying and detecting texts from an image.

5.3.1 Software specification

Android

Android is a mobile operating system based on a modified version of the Linux kernel and other open-source software, designed primarily for touchscreen mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets.

The Android platform allows developers to write managed code using Java to manage and control the Android device. Android applications can be developed by using the Java programming language and the Android SDK.

Text-To-Speech Engine

The text-to-speech (TTS) is a type of assistive technology that reads digital text aloud. With a click of a button or the touch of a finger, TTS can take words on a computer or other digital device and convert them into audio.

Synthesizes speech from text for immediate playback or to create a sound file.

Keras-GPU v2.3.1

The Keras-GPU was chosen in conjunction to perform the calculations on the GPU and not on the CPU. This significantly reduced the time of sending the scanned text frames to the remote google computer vision API and reproducing the required text onto the camera interface.

5.4 Experiment Results

In this section of the project, the investigations and the corresponding evaluations are presented.

The OCR application accuracy is defined as the ratio of correct recognized characters to the total number of characters (samples) tested, as shown below:

$$\text{OCR Accuracy} = (\text{No. of Correctly Recognized Characters} / \text{Total No. of Characters Tested}) \times 100\%$$

A number of experiments and test conditions were accomplished on (13650) samples to measure the performance of the proposed OCR system on various types of document images of different dimensions, font types and font sizes. As a result, the database size of training samples is computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{No. of training samples} &= \text{No. of Samples} \times \text{No. of Fonts} \times \text{No. of Font Sizes} \\ &= 91 \times 5 \times 7 = 3185 \text{ samples} \end{aligned}$$

A more appropriate comparison can be made if both DCT & Wavelet methods are measured under identical conditions. Based on the results shown in Table (2) below, one can deduce that all wavelet features produce better recognition rates 96% (from 92 - 98%) than DCT features 92% (from 87 - 95%). Different number of DCT coefficients (N) and wavelet decomposition levels values are examined according to the recognition rates. It is clearly indicated that two decomposition levels are most appropriate for wavelet feature vector construction, whereas 10-DCT coefficients is the suitable number of DCT features (N=10).

Test Image File	Font Type	No. of Chars	DCT			Wavelet Transform		
			N=5	N=10	N=15	Level1	Level2	Level3
Test1.bmp	Arial	525	77.52	91.62	85.90	71.43	94.29	80.95
Test2.bmp		581	79.00	93.46	87.44	74.87	96.73	87.78
Test3.bmp		791	81.29	90.90	85.59	80.28	94.82	85.59
Test4.bmp		371	75.74	94.88	83.83	64.15	97.30	80.32
Test5.bmp		462	71.65	87.88	78.35	69.05	93.51	83.77
Test6.bmp	Calibri	480	76.46	92.29	82.29	75.63	95.00	83.75
Test7.bmp		633	79.78	93.84	85.47	77.09	95.10	80.73
Test8.bmp		415	78.31	95.66	84.10	68.43	96.63	83.37
Test9.bmp		692	79.05	90.75	83.38	75.29	96.68	85.55
Test10.bmp		510	77.06	92.75	84.31	79.02	97.25	84.90
Test11.bmp	Courier New	395	75.70	92.41	82.28	67.34	96.46	81.27
Test12.bmp		704	81.82	95.60	86.36	73.86	97.30	84.52
Test13.bmp		620	79.35	92.58	83.23	75.97	96.61	83.71
Test14.bmp		557	79.35	93.36	84.02	74.33	98.20	89.23
Test15.bmp		454	75.11	91.63	81.28	68.06	96.92	82.60
Test16.bmp	Lucida Sans	664	80.72	93.67	86.30	75.75	95.63	84.19
Test17.bmp		325	72.92	94.46	82.15	68.92	92.62	79.38
Test18.bmp		653	78.56	92.04	82.54	76.11	94.49	82.24
Test19.bmp		341	68.62	89.15	77.71	69.21	95.60	78.01
Test20.bmp		747	79.65	91.30	82.33	78.71	94.38	83.53
Test21.bmp	Times New Roman	720	76.11	90.28	79.44	77.64	96.81	85.00
Test22.bmp		373	71.05	87.13	80.43	72.12	98.93	86.33
Test23.bmp		475	73.68	89.05	79.79	68.63	95.37	80.63
Test24.bmp		525	79.05	93.14	82.86	74.10	96.95	85.52
Test25.bmp		637	78.02	90.74	81.48	78.96	97.02	86.81
Total		13650	77.64	92.05	83.16	74.25	96.01	83.89

5.4.1 Validation Results

To validate the accuracy of the text recognition from the read-for-me application, a set of new images containing text were passed through the application and the results were as seen in the predictions below which indicate a class prediction accuracy of about 90%.

RESPONSORIAL PSALM

Ps 93 : labe.id-2.5 (R. of. la) R.

R. The Lord reigns, he is robed in majesty.

The Lord is king, with majesty enrobed.
The Lord has robed himself with might, he has girded himself with power.

The world you made firm, not to be moved, your throne has stood firm from of old.

From all eternity, O Lord, you are R.
Tuly your decrees are to be trusted.
Holiness is fitting to your house,
O Lord, until the end of time. R.

SECOND READING

Revelation 1:5-8

"The ruler of the kings on earth... made us a kingdom, priests to his God."

A reading from the Book of Revelation
Jesus Christ, is the faithful witness, the first-born of the dead, and the ruler of kings on earth. To him who loves us and has freed us from our sins by his blood and made us a kingdom, priests to his God and Father, to him be glory and dominion for ever and ever. Amen. Behold, he is coming with the clouds, and every eye will see him, every one who pierced him; and all tribes of the earth will wail on account of him. Even so. Amen. "I am the Alpha and the Omega," says the Lord God, who is and who was and who is to come, the Almighty.

The word of the Lord.

GOSPEL

John 18:33b-37

"You say that I am a king."
A reading from the holy Gospel according to John
At that time, Pilate said to Jesus, "Are you the King of the Jews?" Jesus answered, "Do you say this of your own accord, or did others say it to you about me?" Pilate answered, "Am I a Jew? Your own nation and the chief priests

Step 4: Writing the Introduction.

Step 4: Writing the Introduction.

The introduction is the most general part of the essay. It helps to provide a roadmap for further discussion. The following are guidelines for writing the basic introduction.

- **Definition:** identify, define, and/or describe the topic, concept or literary theme. What will you talk about? (Theme: "What will you talk about?")
- **Relevance:** show the importance of your topic, concept or theme. How does it relate to or impact society? (Does it relate to or impact society?)
- **Thesis:** copy the thesis statement you generated in the previous step whose break down is the following.

Illustration:

- Topic-** "Laughter in my family."
- Definition-** "Laughter is a part of everyday human experience expressed vocally as Ha Ha Ha. It helps build positive experiences between individuals as Ha Ha Ha! It helps build positive experiences between individuals."
- Relevance-** "Laughter is the best medicine for overcoming anger and breaking it makes people happier, more relaxed, and better in coping with everyday challenges."
- Thesis Statement-** "Laughter has always been an important part of my family. It has helped us get comfortable after long separations, made it easier to overcome difficult times, and has served as a form of entertainment."

Step 5: Writing the Body of the Essay

Step 5: Writing the Body of the Essay

The body of the essay is the most detailed part. It involves addressing each supporting detail in a separate, fully developed paragraph. Make sure to include all the necessary details, illustrations, statistics, anecdotes and examples to support the claim.

It is important that each supporting detail be announced or introduced within the text. This announcement or introduction is called a **topic sentence** and is found at the beginning of a paragraph. The topic sentence is a statement made about supporting details.

Thus, basing on the above, here are examples/illustrations:

- **Topic sentence 1:** Laughter has helped my family create a comfort zone, making it easier to reconnect after long separations.
- **Topic sentence 2:** Laughter has helped us to cope during the most difficult times, making the process of unbearable situations.
- **Topic sentence 3:** Finally, laughter and jokes keep us entertained, while strengthening our family bond.

UGANDA CHRISTIAN UNIVERSITY

A Centre of Excellence in the Heart of Africa
A Centre of Excellence in the Heart of Africa

Minella

Writing and Study Skills: Writing and Study Skills

A Foundation Course at Uganda Christian University
A Poundation Course at Uganda Christinn University

Pioneer Editors:

Eleanor J. Daniels, Peggy Noll
Eleanor J. Daniels, Peggy Noll

Contributors 2013-2014 Edition:

Richard Watiraho, Mary Kusemererwa, Abel Kibbedi Wankuma, Jamie Cardwell,
Mary Kusemererwa, Abel Kibbedi Wankuma, Jamie Cardwell,
David Bakanya, Monya Ngepe, Maureen Kabasingu, Evangeline Nalugya, Stella
Dean Bulaid Nuene, Maureen Kabasingu, Evangeline Nalugya, Stella
Wanyambuka, Bernard Ochan, Faith Pacumbo, Priscilla Namirimu, Edison Etori,
Bernard Ociken, Faith Paruthi, Priscilla Namirimu, Edison Etori,
Pamela Tumwacha, Mary Naitala Oror, Daniel Omaya, Lillian Tindye bwa, Ivan
Taba Mary Naitala Oror, Daniel Omaya, Lillian Tindye bwa, Ivan
Mugisha, Emmanuel Etabu (Cover Page)
Mugisha, anse: tabu KCover Pag

Department of Languages and Literature
Department of Lang and Literature
© 2014 Uganda Christian University
© 2014 Uganda Christian University

5.5 Conclusion

The read-for-me ocr application for 3185 training samples and 13650 testing samples is presented that relies on DCT and wavelet features. Image enhancement techniques (noise removal, foreground/ background separation, normalization and binarization) are adopted in this work prior to segmentation in order to improve the recognition rates and simplify the process of characters segmentation. It is found that wavelet method is appropriate for feature vector construction where all the recognition rates (96%) outperform the DCT based recognition method (92%). To enhance the recognition rates further and speeds up the recognition process, text-components (characters, digits, and symbols) are classified according to the proportion of (H/W) feature that produce 99% accuracy for wavelet- based method because it helps distinguish a class from other classes which is invariant to different font sizes of the same font type.

Chapter Six: Limitation, Conclusion, and Future Work

This chapter discusses the limitations during implementation, the conclusion and the proposed future work to be undertaken to improve the system.

6.1 Limitation

Though the proposed system does perform well on being able to scan text from any digitally printed text documents, there is still room for the improvement compared with some of the state-of-the-art OCR applications.

One challenge faced was with scanning hand written text which makes it difficult for the application to categorize or classify the fonts since the way we write our texts using pen on paper has no official font assigned to it and therefore for example you might find that some people write the letter 'a' in different ways and so the application finds challenges in reading some of words that have been hand written and properly classifying them.

6.2 Conclusion

In this research project report, I analyzed the current system, tools, literature and algorithms used in text to speech recognition along with identifying some of their weaknesses and because of this, I was able to come up with a localized application by applying some aspects of machine learning using technologies such as the google cloud vision API to come up with a solution that aids the visually impaired people in facilitating their teaching and learning process. The text recognition used helps in reading and analyzing text and providing feedback in form of speech. I then validate the system using data inform of text and speech output from both the visually impaired and normal sighted people so as to check the usefulness of the application. Results show that the proposed solution achieved comparable performance and has great potential to serve the visually challenged people with a better assistant.

6.3 Future Work

In the future, I will continue the work on improving the system to include local currency value detection as well as a more accurate handwritten text recognition for better dynamicity converted to speech in order to ease the lives of the visually impaired throughout their educational journeys and facilitate their learning and personal study process.

References

- (2019). Retrieved from keras_ocr: <https://keras-ocr.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- Abner, & Lahm, G. (2002). Implementation of assistive technology with students who are visually impaired: teacher' readiness. *Journal of visual impairment and Blindness*, 96, 97-112.
- Arter, C. (1997). Listening Skills, in Mason, H & McCall. *Visual Impairment access to education for children and young people*.
- Avanthika, U., Sundar, S., & Nancy, S. (2015). An Interactive Mobile Application for Visually Impaired to Have Access to Listening Audio Books with Handy Books Portal. *International journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*.
- Braille, L. (2021, may 13). *Braille Education System*. Retrieved from wikipedia: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Braille>
- Combination of Document Image Binarization Techniques. (2011). *International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition*.
- Dhavare, U., & Kulkarni, U. (2015). Natural Language Processing using Artificial Intelligence. *International Journal of Emerging Trends & Technology in Computer Science*, 203-205.
- Felix, S., Kumar, S., & Veeramuthu, A. (2018). A Smart Personal AI Assistant for Visually Impaired People. *2nd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, 1245-1250.
- Fonte F, A., Nistal, M., & Rial, J. C. (2016). NLAST A natural language assistant. *IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference* , (pp. 709-713).
- Kumar, M., Chandar, P., Prasad, A., & Sumangali, K. (2016). Android-based educational Chatbot for visually impaired . *IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Computing Research (ICIC)*, (pp. 1-4).
- M, K. S., Swathi, M., & Shetty, M. (2019). Assistance System for Visually Impaired using AI. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY*.
- mediacentre factsheets*. (2017, October). Retrieved from Mediacentre: <http://www.who.int/meiacentre/factsheets/fs282/en.,October>

Parkhi, S., Dr Lokhande, S., & Thombare, N. (2016). Vocal Vision Android Application for Visually Impaired Person. *International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research Vol. V, 6*.

Pearl, C. (2016). *Designing voice user interfaces - principles of conversational experiences*. O'Reilly Media Inc.

Pranob, C. K., Harish, V., & Swathi, M. (2012). A review on the Various Techniques used for Optical Character Recognition. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA)*, 2248-9622.

Tariq, J., & Umar, N. M. (2010). a-Soft: An English Language OCR. *Second International Conference on Computer Engineering and Applications*.

Wikipedia Agile Software Development. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agile_software_development

Abner & Lahm, G., 2002. Implementation of assistive technology with students who are visually impaired: teacher' readiness. *Journal of visual impairment and Blindness*, pp. 96, 97-112.

Anon., 2010. *Understanding the Extreme Programming Life Cycle Phases*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.brighthubpm.com/methods-strategies/88996-the-extreme-programming-life-cycle/#:~:text=The%20Extreme%20Programming%20software%20development,coding%2C%20testing%2C%20and%20listening>.

Anon., 2011. *Combination of Document Image Binarization Techniques*. s.l., s.n.

Anon., 2017. *mediacentre factsheets*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.who.int/meiacentre/factsheets/fs282/en.,October>

Anon., 2019. [Online] Available at: <https://keras-ocr.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Anon., 2020. *fast facts on common eye disorders*. [Online] Available at:

<https://www.cdc.gov/visionhealth/basics/ced/fastfacts.htm#:~:text=Approximately%2012%20million%20people%2040,du%20to%20uncorrected%20refractive%20error.>

Anon., n.d. *Wikipedia Agile Software Development*. [Online]
Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agile_software_development

Arter, C., 1997. Listening Skills, in Mason, H & McCall. *Visual Impairment access to education for children and young people*.

Avanthika, U., Sundar, S. & Nancy, S., 2015. An Interactive Mobile Application for Visually Impaired to Have Access to Listening Audio Books with Handy Books Portal. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*.

Azimi, A., 2017. *Extreme Programming*. [Online]
Available at: <https://medium.com/@azimidev/extreme-programming-xp-35223784976e>

Braille, L., 2021. *Braille Education System*. [Online]
Available at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Braille>

Dhavare, U. & Kulkarni, U., 2015. Natural Language Processing using Artificial Intelligence. *International Journal of Emerging Trends & Technology in Computer Science*, pp. 203-205.

Felix, S., Kumar, S. & Veeramuthu, A., 2018. A Smart Personal AI Assistant for Visually Impaired People. *2nd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, pp. 1245-1250.

Fonte F, A., Nistal, M. & Rial, J. C. B., 2016. *NLAST A natural language assistant*. s.l., s.n., pp. 709-713.

Jonathan, H. S., 2016. *TeensHealth*. [Online]
Available at: <https://kidshealth.org/en/teens/visual-impairment.html#:~:text=Visual%20impairment%20is%20a%20term,have%20what's%20called%20legal%20blindness.>

[Accessed 24 February 2022].

Kazibwe, K., 2016. *Trending news*. [Online]
Available at: <https://chimpreports.com/1-4-million-ugandans-have-eye-defects-health-ministry/>

KM, W., 2010. Childhood blindness and low vision in Uganda. In: s.l.:s.n., pp. 184-192.

Kumar, M., Chandar, P., Prasad, A. & Sumangali, K., 2016. *Android-based educational Chatbot for visually impaired*. s.l., s.n., pp. 1-4.

M, K. S., Swathi, M. & Shetty, M., 2019. Assistance System for Visually Impaired using AI. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY*.

Parkhi, S., Dr Lokhande, S. & Thombare, N., 2016. Vocal Vision Android Application for Visually Impaired Person. *International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research Vol. V*, p. 6.

Pearl, C., 2016. *Designing voice user interfaces - principles of conversational experiences*. s.l.:O'Reilly Media Inc.

Pranob, C. K., Harish, V. & Swathi, M., 2012. A review on the Various Techniques used for Optical Character Recognition. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA)*, pp. 2248-9622.

Shahed, A. S. & Md, H. A., 2016. *Blind Reader: An Intelligent Assistant for Blind* 19th *International Conference on Computer and Information Technology*. Dhaka Bangladesh, s.n.

Smaradottir, M. & Haland, 2017. Evaluation of touchscreen assistive technology for visually disabled users. *IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications*, pp. 248-253.

Tariq, J. & Umar, N. M. U. N., 2010. *a-Soft: An English Language OCR*. s.l., s.n.

Appendix

OCR: Optical Character Recognition

DCT: Discrete Cosine Transformation

API: Application Programming Interface